

Annex - Air pollution sampler

Children's and parents' modal choice when commuting to primary school and air pollution burden: Is there a healthier way to commute?

Dominika Tóthová^{a*}, Ondřej Mikeš^b, Vilém Pařil^c, Petr Tonev^d

^a*Department of Regional Economics, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

^b*RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

^c*Institute for Transport Economics, Geography and Policy, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

^d*Department of Regional Economics, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

*Dominika Tóthová, dominika.tothova@econ.muni.cz Department of Regional Economics, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

Annex

Table 1. Air pollution personal sampler specification

Parameter	Specification
Sensors	Sensirion SPS30, SCD40-D-R2
CO ₂ Concentration	400 – 2000 ppm, accuracy ±50 ppm
Particulate Matter (PM ₁ /PM _{2.5})	Range: 0 – 1000 µg/m ³ , accuracy: 0-100 µg/m ³ ±10 µg/m ³ ; 100-1000 µg/m ³ ±10%
Particulate Matter (PM ₄ /PM ₁₀)	Range: 0 – 1000 µg/m ³ , accuracy: 0-100 µg/m ³ ±25 µg/m ³ ; 100-1000 µg/m ³ ±25%
Temperature	-10°C to +60°C, accuracy ±0.8 °C
Humidity	0 – 100% RH, accuracy ±6% RH
Communication	GPRS 2G, SIM 1024MB / prepaid 1GB/10 years
Internal Memory	512 kB
Battery	3.7 V / 2800 mAh, 20-hour operational time, USB-C charging
Dimensions	85 x 95 x 20 mm
Weight	200 g